

Species 1: *H. hecalesia*

PC1, PNT.index: 0.18; moderate PNT

NOT test

Species 2: *H. hortense*

PC1, PNT.index: 0.08; some PNT

Environmental overlap

PC1
Red=S1>S2, Blue=S1<S2, Cor. Uncorrected= 0.426

Equivalency

Niche Similarity:
D= 0.421

Background 2->1

Background 1->2

Species 1: *H. hecalesia*

PC1, PNT.index: 0.13; some PNT

NDT overlap

PC1, PNT.index: 0.31; high PNT

Species 2: *H. hortense*

Environmental overlap

PC1
Red=S1>S2, Blue=S1<S2, Cor. Uncorrected= 0.446

Equivalency

Niche Similarity:
D= 0.48

Background 2->1

D
p.value = 0.01818

Background 1->2

D
p.value = 0.03226